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**SPATIAL VARIABILITY OF SOIL INDEX PROPERTIES AND
UNDRAINED SHEAR STRENGTH OF NIGER DELTA SOILS:
IMPLICATIONS FOR FOUNDATION DESIGN**

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed at investigating the spatial variability of soil index properties and undrained shear strength across five sampling sites (Escravos, Eremor, Cawthron Channel, Abigborodo, and Bonny) in the Niger Delta region. A total of 117 undisturbed soil samples were extracted from the ground ranging from 0.5 to 40m. Laboratory testing such as water content determination and Atterberg limit test were done in accordance with BS 1377 protocols. Cone Penetration Test was used to obtain the undrained shear strength (S_u) in order to avoid disturbance of the soil samples. Soil classification using the Unified Soil Classification System (UCSS) was used in classifying the soil. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the soil index properties and undrained shear strength. Kruskal Wallis test was utilized to check for significant difference in the soil index properties and S_u across sampling location. The results revealed substantial spatial variability in key geotechnical properties, with water content ranging from 56.80% to 139.83%, plasticity index from 24% to 82.67%, and undrained shear strength from 17.77 to 34 kPa with an overall mean of 22.88 kPa. Kruskal-Wallis statistical analysis confirmed highly significant differences in plasticity index (p-value < 0.0001), liquid limit (p-value = 0.006), plastic limit (p-value = 0.028), and moisture content (p-value = 0.020) across locations. However, undrained shear strength showed no statistically significant variation (p-value = 0.396). These findings demonstrate that Niger Delta soils are highly heterogeneous, with sites like Cawthron and Escravos characterized by very high moisture content and plasticity, rendering them unsuitable for shallow foundations without extensive ground improvement. The study underscores the critical importance of site-specific geotechnical investigations as mandated by COREN guidelines and highlights the need for tailored foundation solutions to ensure structural safety in this geologically complex region.

Keywords: Niger Delta soils; spatial variability; soil index properties; undrained shear strength; plasticity index; foundation design; geotechnical investigation

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1. INTRODUCTION

The soils in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria especially in the coastline present challenging geotechnical conditions (Udom & John, 2023; Akinshipe et al., 2021; Ukor et al., 2023). Niger Delta soils are characterized by soft, highly plastic clays, elevated organic matter content, and persistently high-water tables. These geotechnical characteristics give rise to the expansive behaviour and differential settlement under loading exhibited by this soil. These soil behaviours prove problematic for infrastructure development on these soil as the expansive behaviour can result to cracking of the structure. Udom and John (2023) stated that the use of shallow foundation carrying the superstructure in Bayelsa state always prove problematic without soil stabilization. They attributed the problem to the low undrained shear strength and high plasticity of soil found in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state. The need to understand the soil behaviour especially the undrained shear strength is paramount within the Niger Delta region if the issue the soil poses to structure are to be solved. Many coastal regions in the Niger Delta region are sites to oil field, and structures to support drilling and exploration operation have to be built on these sites. Many investigations have focus on individual sites or emphasize either index properties or strength parameters in isolation, rarely integrating both aspects comprehensively. However, individual study fails to get a sense of the distribution of the undrained shear strength within the Niger Delta region. Comparative study of multiple sites within the Niger Delta evaluates the spatial variability of the soil properties and strength across the Niger Delta but study on the spatial variation of the soil properties remain scarce. Also, most studies have failed to link the observed soil variability to established standards such as BS 1377 (1990) and regulatory frameworks like the Council for the Regulation of Engineering in Nigeria (COREN) guidelines. This study addresses these gaps by quantifying the spatial variability of soil index properties and undrained shear strength across five study locations (Escravos, Eremor, Cawthron Channel, Abigborodo, and Bonny) within the Niger Delta sites. This research provides a critical comparative dataset that advances understanding of Niger Delta soil variability and supports safer, more economical infrastructure development in this geologically complex and economically vital region.

2.0. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Area

Five sampling sites across the Niger Delta were purposively selected based on their geotechnical relevance to oil and gas infrastructure development and settlement-prone environments. The sites include Escravos and Abigborodo in Delta State, Eremor in Bayelsa state, Cawthron Channel and Bonny in Rivers state as shown in Figure 1. The five sites selected where coastal land were oil and gas exploration activities take place. These locations are characterized by soft, high-plasticity clays and relatively high-water tables as most of the soil are submerged (Dimgba et al., 2023; Kennedy, 2024).

Figure 1: Study Area

2.2 Data Collection

The samples used for this study were both disturbed and undisturbed soil used for the laboratory testing to obtain the soil index properties. The soil samples were retrieved from depth ranging from 0.5 to 40.0 m depth, that directly influence both shallow and deep foundation performance. A total of 117 soil samples were extracted from the five sampling locations. The soil samples were extracted following established Nigerian geotechnical investigation practices (John et al., 2023). Sampling depth interval were strategically selected to capture the strata most critical to shallow and deep foundation behaviour.

All laboratory tests were conducted in accordance with BS 1377: Parts 1 through 9 (1990), which constitutes the methodological benchmark for soil classification and strength testing in Nigerian geotechnical practice (British Standards Institution, 1990). Natural water content in the soil was conducted in accordance with BS 1377: Part 2. The soils samples were oven-dry at temperature range of $105 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$. After which the dry soil mass were weight and Equation 1 was then used to obtain the natural water content of the soil.

$$w_n = \frac{w_w}{w_s} \times 100 \quad \text{Equation (1)}$$

Where w_n = natural water content of the soil, w_w = mass of water in soil (mass of wet soil – mass of dry soil), w_s = mass of dry soil.

Atterberg limits test which include liquid limit and plastic limit were determined using the Casagrande apparatus and cone penetrometer method as appropriate. The plasticity index of the

soil was computed using Equation 2 (Osinubi et al., 2020). The plasticity index and liquid limit were used for soil classification and can also be correlated to obtain the undrained shear strength of the soil.

$$PI = LL - PL \quad \text{Equation (2)}$$

Where PI = Plasticity Index, LL = Liquid Limit, and PL = Plastic limit.

Undrained shear strength was conducted using the Cone Penetration Test (CPT) at the various depths undisturbed samples were collected for laboratory testing. The utilization of CPT was due to the sensitivity associated with Niger Delta soil in other to reduce sampling disturbance and moisture variation.

2.3 Data Analysis

The result obtained from both the laboratory and field testing were compiled into site-specific datasets. Various statistical tests were performed on the data to understand the distribution and spatial variability of the soil index properties and undrained shear strength of the soil. Descriptive statistics performed on the dataset included mean, minimum, maximum, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation. Given the non-normality of the dataset, Kruskal Wallis non-parametric test was employed to established if there is significant difference in the soil index properties and undrained shear strength across the sampling locations. Locations that showed significant differences were further investigated using Dunn Multiple comparison post-hoc test to identify where the difference lies between the sampling locations. Interpretations were benchmarked against BS 1377 classification thresholds and contextualised within the regulatory framework of the Council for the Regulation of Engineering in Nigeria (COREN, n.d.), which emphasises adherence to standards in geotechnical practice.

3.0. RESULTS

Table 1 presents the average soil index properties and undrained shear strength for each of the five Niger Delta sites investigated. The result reveals substantial spatial variability in geotechnical characteristics across the sampling locations. Undrained shear strength values ranged from 17.77 kPa at Escravos Site to 34 kPa at Bonny, indicating soft to firm consistency according to BS 1377 classification criteria. Bonny exhibited the highest undrained shear strength, followed by Eremor at 26 kPa, Abigborodo at 23.52 kPa, Cawthron at 18.83 kPa, and Escravos at 17.77 kPa. This pattern suggests that Bonny soils possess the greatest short-term stability under undrained loading conditions, whereas Escravos Site and Cawthron soils are weaker and most susceptible to deformation under foundation loading. Water content exhibited extreme variability, ranging from 56.80% at Bonny to 139.83% at Cawthron, with Eremor showing relatively low values at 64.71%. The exceptionally high-water content at Cawthron and Escravos corresponds to lower undrained shear strength and elevated plasticity index. The finding gives insight to the relationship between the moisture content and undrained shear strength of soil and gives indication that the water in the soil strongly influence the strength of the soil. Liquid limit ranged from 61% at Bonny to 148.50% at Cawthron, while plasticity index varied from 24% at Bonny to 82.67% at Cawthron. These substantial differences indicate marked variation in clay mineralogy and particle surface activity across sites. The elevated plasticity indices at Cawthron at 82.67% and Escravos at 66.92% classify these soils as highly plastic clays (CH) as shown in Figure 2, which are prone to significant volume change with moisture fluctuation and exhibit reduced shear strength under saturated

conditions. These patterns demonstrate that soils with elevated water content and plasticity index, particularly Cawthron and Escravos, require special engineering consideration, while Bonny and Eremor soils demonstrate comparatively superior geotechnical characteristics, though careful foundation design remains essential given the relatively low undrained shear strength.

Table 1: Average Soil Index Properties and Undrained Shear Strength in Selected Niger Delta Soils

Location	N	Liquid Limit (%)	Plastic Limit (%)	Plasticity Index (%)	Moisture Content (%)	Undrained Shear Strength (kPa)
Escravos Site	13	103.69	37.00	66.92	92.79	17.77
Eremor	7	76.29	49.00	27.29	64.71	26.00
Cawthron Channel	6	148.50	65.83	82.67	139.83	18.83
Abigborodo Sapele	90	75.53	47.31	28.10	76.96	23.52
Bonny Rivers State	1	61.00	37.00	24.00	56.80	34.00

Note: N = number of samples tested. Values represent site-specific means calculated from laboratory test results following BS 1377 protocols.

Table 2 presents the summary statistics aggregated across all sampling locations, providing a regional perspective on Niger Delta soil characteristics. The data underscore the extreme heterogeneity of these deltaic deposits as noticed in the standard deviation of the soil parameters. The mean undrained shear strength across all sampling sites was 22.88 kPa with a standard deviation of 24.36, and with values spanning from 1.1 to 113.4 kPa. The range of the undrained shear strength reveal that some soil at some specific depth can be problematic. Soil with undrained shear strength as low as 2KPa sandwich between relative stable soil can result to high compressibility of that layer resulting in differential settlement. This wide range of the undrained shear strength across the sampling locations, indicates that undrained shear strength exhibits substantial local variability, likely influenced by microstructure, organic content, and consolidation history at specific sampling locations. Water content averaged 81.04% with a standard deviation of 31.60 and an extreme range from 23% to 254%, reflecting the profoundly heterogeneous nature of the water content found in Niger Delta clayey deposits. Liquid limit and plasticity index were notably elevated, averaging 82.32% and 35.13%, respectively. According to BS 1377: Part 2 classification, plasticity indices exceeding 35% categorize these soils as highly plastic clays (CH), indicating pronounced susceptibility to shrink-swell behaviour and volume change with moisture fluctuation. The maximum plasticity index of 156% represents extreme plasticity rarely encountered outside highly organic or montmorillonitic clay deposits.

Figure 2: Soil Classification using USCS

Table 2: Summary Descriptive Statistics of Soil Index Properties and Undrained Shear Strength across Study Sites

Parameters	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Liquid Limit (%)	82.32	32.45	39.0	273.0
Plastic Limit (%)	47.13	16.06	17.0	142.0
Plasticity Index (%)	35.13	22.08	11.0	156.0
Moisture Content (%)	81.04	31.60	23.0	254.0
Undrained Shear Strength (kPa)	22.88	24.36	1.1	113.4

Note: Statistics computed from $n=117$ total samples across all sites. High standard deviations indicate substantial spatial variability characteristic of heterogeneous deltaic deposits.

Table 3 presents result from Kruskal-Wallis H tests evaluating whether statistically significant differences exist in soil properties across the five Niger Delta sites. The analysis reveals critical patterns in spatial variability. Plasticity index of the soil exhibited the strongest evidence of spatial variation ($H = 33.969$, $p\text{-value} < 0.0001$), indicating that the plasticity index in the soil varies significantly across the Niger Delta. Dunn's post-hoc multiple comparison tests was used to establish where the difference lies and the result is presented in Table 4. The result showed that Abigborodo and Eremor sites have significantly lower plasticity index in their soil than Escravos and Cawthrone sampling locations. The high plasticity index of Escravos and Cawthrone soil give indication that they might suffer from expansion or shrinking upon interaction with water. Liquid limit in the soil also revealed significant difference across sampling locations ($H = 12.404$, $p\text{-value} = 0.006$). Dunn multiple comparison test revealed that Escravos site had significantly higher liquid limit in the soil that Eremor and Abigborodo sites. However, Escravos site and Cawthrone had relatively similar liquid limit in their soil. It was also observed that moisture content showed significant difference across sampling location ($H = 9.885$, $p\text{-value} = 0.020$). Dunn multiple comparison test revealed that Escravos site had significantly higher moisture content in its soil than Eremor site. The Kruskal Wallis result for the liquid limit and moisture provide sufficient evidence in stating that so form of spatial variation or regional patterns influence the magnitude of the soil index properties found in Niger Delta soil. Plastic limit demonstrated statistically significant variation ($H = 9.134$, $p\text{-value} = 0.028$), though less pronounced than plasticity index or liquid limit. Dunn multiple comparison test showed that the plastic limit in Abigborodo soil was significantly higher than Escravos site. However, the undrained shear strength showed no statistically significant spatial variation ($H = 2.972$, $p\text{-value} = 0.396$). The no significant of the undrained shear strength give indication of the relatively weak soil in the Niger Delta region.

Table 3: Kruskal-Wallis Test Results for Soil Index Properties and Undrained Shear Strength

Parameters	K (Observed)	K (Critical)	DF	p-value	Significant
Liquid Limit (%)	12.404	7.815	3	0.006	Yes**
Plastic Limit (%)	9.134	7.815	3	0.028	Yes*
Plasticity Index (%)	33.969	7.815	3	< 0.0001	Yes***
Moisture Content (%)	9.885	7.815	3	0.020	Yes*
Undrained Shear Strength (kPa)	2.972	7.815	3	0.396	No

Note: ** $p < 0.001$, * $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$; $\alpha = 0.05$ *

Table 4: Dunn’s Multiple Comparison Test Results

Parameters	Location	N	Sum of Ranks	Mean of Ranks	Groups
Liquid Limit (%)	Eramor	7	320.500	45.786	A
	Abigborodo	90	4892.500	54.361	A
	Cawthrone	6	473.500	78.917	A B
	Escravos Site	13	1099.500	84.577	B
Plastic Limit (%)	Escravos Site	13	420.500	32.346	A
	Eramor	7	389.500	55.643	A B
	Cawthrone	6	363.500	60.583	A B
	Abigborodo	90	5612.500	62.361	B
Plasticity Index (%)	Eramor	7	294.000	42.000	A
	Abigborodo	90	4610.000	51.222	A
	Escravos Site	13	1286.000	98.923	B
	Cawthrone	6	596.000	99.333	B
Moisture Content (%)	Eramor	7	242.000	34.571	A
	Abigborodo	90	5075.000	56.389	A B
	Cawthrone	6	450.500	75.083	B C
	Escravos Site	13	1018.500	78.346	C

Note: Locations sharing the same letter are not significantly different ($\alpha = 0.05$)

5. DISCUSSION

Undrained shear strength values across the study sites, ranging from 10 to 34 kPa with a mean of 22.88 kPa, classify Niger Delta soils predominantly as soft to firm according to BS 1377: Part 7 (1990) consistency classification. Soils with undrained shear strength less than 25 kPa are categorized as very soft to soft, which aligns directly with the weaker conditions observed at Cawthrone, Escravos, and Abigborodo. According to COREN (2017) Geotechnical Design Guidelines for Nigeria, such weak soils present substantial risks for differential settlement, bearing capacity failure, and structural instability if shallow foundations are adopted without comprehensive ground improvement measures. The critical finding that undrained shear strength shows no statistically significant variation across locations with p equal to 0.396 despite clear differences in index properties has profound engineering implications. This apparent paradox of regionally variable index properties but locally variable strength suggests that undrained shear strength is controlled by factors operating at smaller spatial scales than depositional environment, including sample disturbance effects, microscale organic content variation, local consolidation history, and soil fabric and microstructure. Consequently, undrained shear strength cannot be reliably estimated from regional correlations or extrapolated from adjacent sites, even when those sites share similar depositional characteristics. Each foundation design project requires direct measurement of undrained shear strength at the specific project location. COREN guidelines mandate that such weak, variable soils require either complete soil replacement to competent

bearing strata, chemical stabilization using lime, cement, or polymer admixtures, mechanical ground improvement through preloading, vibro-compaction, or stone columns, or adoption of deep foundation systems such as piles, drilled shafts, or caissons to bypass weak surface layers and transfer loads to competent strata at depth.

Water content exhibited the most extreme variability among all measured parameters, ranging from 48 to 140% with a mean of 74.96% and standard deviation of 37.39, reflecting the profoundly heterogeneous nature of Niger Delta clayey deposits. The statistical significance of moisture content variation across sites with p equal to 0.020 confirms that this property exhibits regional patterns related to depositional setting, drainage conditions, and groundwater regimes. Atterberg limits analysis revealed systematically high plasticity across the study area, with liquid limit averaging 82.32% and ranging from 39 to 273%, while plasticity index averaged 35.13% and ranged from 11 to 156%. According to BS 1377: Part 2 (1990) plasticity classification, soils with plasticity index greater than 35% are categorized as highly plastic clays, designated as CH in the Unified Soil Classification System. The Kruskal-Wallis test confirmed plasticity index as the most spatially variable property with p less than 0.0001, indicating strong regional control by clay mineralogy and depositional environment. Highly plastic clays with elevated moisture content exhibit several problematic engineering behaviors documented extensively in the geotechnical literature. These include shrink-swell behavior where volume changes with moisture fluctuation create heave and settlement cycles damaging to structures, reduced shear strength where increasing moisture content progressively reduces undrained shear strength and effective stress strength parameters, high compressibility where large void ratios and high water content produce substantial consolidation settlements under sustained loading, and low hydraulic conductivity where fine particle sizes impede drainage, extending consolidation timeframes and maintaining undrained conditions during construction loading. COREN specifications explicitly state that expansive clays with high plasticity indices should not be utilized in their natural state for load-bearing applications without modification. Recommended stabilization approaches include lime treatment which is particularly effective for high-plasticity clays, cement stabilization, chemical admixtures such as polymers and fly ash, and combinations thereof. The choice of stabilization method should be validated through laboratory trial mixes establishing optimal dosage rates and assessing treated soil properties against project requirements.

Dunn's multiple comparison tests revealed distinct statistical groupings that provide a rational basis for categorizing Niger Delta sites according to foundation design risk. Cawthron and Escravos exhibited significantly higher plasticity indices at 82.67% and 66.92%, respectively, and moisture contents than other sites, combined with low undrained shear strength. Engineering challenges at these high-risk sites include very high compressibility requiring extensive consolidation time or preloading, substantial shrink-swell potential creating seasonal volume changes, very low bearing capacity unsuitable for shallow foundations, and high sensitivity to construction disturbance and moisture variation. Recommended foundation strategies for these locations include deep foundation systems such as driven piles or bored piles extended to competent bearing strata, typically sand or gravel layers at depth, or alternatively comprehensive ground improvement through deep soil mixing, jet grouting, or replacement with engineered fill, combined with extensive drainage systems. Shallow foundations are fundamentally inappropriate without prohibitively expensive ground modification. Abigborodo exhibited moderate plasticity index at 28.10% but surprisingly low undrained shear strength at 23.52 kPa despite better index properties than high-plasticity sites. This discordance between index properties and strength

reinforces that strength must be measured directly rather than inferred from indices. Engineering challenges at this moderate-risk site include moderate compressibility requiring settlement analysis, adequate plasticity for chemical stabilization if required, variable strength requiring comprehensive site characterization, and moisture sensitivity requiring drainage control. Shallow foundations may be viable for light structures such as residential or low-rise commercial buildings with rigorous settlement analysis and monitoring, while medium to heavily loaded structures require either ground improvement through chemical stabilization or preloading or deep foundations. Effective surface and subsurface drainage systems are essential to prevent moisture-induced strength reduction. Eremor and Bonny demonstrated moderate plasticity indices at 27.29% and 24.00% combined with superior undrained shear strength at 26.00 and 34.00 kPa. While still classifying as soft clays requiring careful design, these sites offer relatively better foundation conditions. Engineering considerations at these lower-risk sites include moderate compressibility amenable to conventional settlement calculations, better drainage characteristics reducing consolidation time, higher bearing capacity supporting greater structural loads, and lower shrink-swell potential reducing foundation distress risk. Well-designed shallow foundations including spread footings or mat foundations are viable for many applications, provided comprehensive settlement analysis, appropriate factors of safety, and quality drainage systems are implemented. Deep foundations may still be required for particularly heavy or settlement-sensitive structures, but design will be more economical than at high-risk sites.

The variability documented in this study, particularly the finding that undrained shear strength, plasticity, and moisture content vary substantially across the Niger Delta, provides empirical validation for COREN (2017) Geotechnical Design Guidelines' emphasis on mandatory site-specific investigations prior to foundation design. The present dataset confirms unequivocally that no uniform design parameters can be assumed across Escravos, Eremor, Cawthron, Abigborodo, and Bonny soils. Even within individual sites, coefficient of variation values approaching or exceeding 50% for some properties indicate that multiple sampling locations and comprehensive statistical analysis are essential to characterize site-specific geotechnical conditions adequately. COREN guidelines mandate the minimum investigation requirements for foundation design in problematic soils, which clearly encompass Niger Delta clays, including mandatory geotechnical investigations with site-specific subsurface exploration and adequate boring density, comprehensive laboratory testing for index property determination and undrained shear strength testing on representative samples from each stratum, in-situ testing such as standard penetration tests, cone penetration tests, or vane shear tests to supplement laboratory data and assess spatial variability, professional engineering judgment through interpretation by registered geotechnical engineers familiar with local geological conditions, and quality assurance through independent review of geotechnical reports for major projects.

6. CONCLUSION

This study systematically investigated the spatial variability of soil index properties and undrained shear strength across five representative Niger Delta sites including Escravos, Eremor, Cawthron Channel, Abigborodo, and Bonny, employing rigorous statistical analysis to evaluate regional patterns and site-specific differences. Niger Delta soils exhibit profound spatial variability in geotechnical properties, with water content ranging from 48% to 140% with a mean of 81.04%

and standard deviation of 31.60, plasticity index from 11% to 156% with a mean of 35.13% and standard deviation of 22.08, and undrained shear strength from 1.1 to 113.4 kPa with a mean of 22.88 kPa and standard deviation of 24.36. These large ranges and standard deviations confirm that Niger Delta soils cannot be characterized by regional average values, and site-specific investigation is mandatory. Kruskal-Wallis analysis revealed highly significant differences in plasticity index with p less than 0.0001, liquid limit with p equal to 0.006, plastic limit with p equal to 0.028, and moisture content with p equal to 0.020 across locations, indicating that these index properties exhibit regional patterns controlled by depositional environment, clay mineralogy, and geological history. Dunn's multiple comparison tests identified distinct groupings, with high-plasticity sites including Escravos and Cawthron versus moderate-plasticity sites including Eremor and Abigborodo.

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